

TEACHING THE SUBJECT OF MOVEMENT PROBLEMS USING INTERACTIVE METHODS

Anvarjon Sharipovich Rashidov

Associate professor of Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute

Annotation: In this article, the topic "Square of addition and subtraction" is explained using various interactive methods in order to make students more interested in the lesson. "Find your neighbor" method was used to reinforce the topic. "Schulte table" method was used to find out whether the students understood the new topic.

Key words: mathematics, unity, polynomial, square of sum and difference, short multiplication formulas.

Introduction. One of the requirements for the organization of education today is to achieve high results in a short time without spending too much mental and physical effort. In order to deliver certain theoretical knowledge to students in a short period of time, to create skills and competences in certain activities, as well as to control the activities of students, to evaluate the level of knowledge, skills and competences acquired by them, teachers are required to be highly pedagogical. requires a new approach to skills and training. Why exactly a short time? Because the student cannot focus on the lesson for a very long time, he gets bored and distracted quickly. Therefore, the teacher should be able to attract the student's attention and explain the content of the topic to the student in a short period of time.

"Mathematics cannot be rapidly developed with yesterday's teaching method. Therefore, it is necessary to create educational programs based on foreign methods that have given good results in practice and retrain teachers. The methodology should be such that it instills a love for mathematics in students. For this, students need to understand that this subject is necessary in life, in every field. "Young people should study not to pass the exam, but to become an educated specialist," said the head of our state. It follows from this idea that we, pedagogues, should be more demanding of ourselves. The main goal of pedagogical technologies in education is to bring the student to the center of the lesson process in the teaching system, to move away from automatic repetitions, to develop independent and creative activity, and to turn him into an active participant of the lesson. Only then students will have their own opinion on important life achievements and problems, practical application of the topics covered. He can justify his point of view.

Pedagogical technology is inherently subjective. Regardless of the form, method and means of organization, technologies:

increase the effectiveness of pedagogical activity;

to decide on mutual cooperation between the teacher and the student;
to ensure the acquisition of thorough knowledge of educational subjects by students;
formation of independent, free and creative thinking skills in students;
creating the necessary conditions for students to realize their potential;
it is necessary to guarantee the priority of democratic and humanitarian ideas in the pedagogical process.

Currently, when it comes to the implementation of new methods or innovations in the educational process, the use of interactive methods is understood. Interactivity is the activity of two people, that is, the learning-knowledge process is mutual activity, movement, and affectiveness, it takes place in the dialogue between the student and the teacher. The main goal of the interactive method is to create the most favorable situation for the educational process. At the same time, it consists in preparing students for international evaluation criteria, developing students' creative thinking in the context of information [1,2].

In this article, some comments and methodical instructions are given on the teaching of the topic "Problems related to motion" known in the mathematics curriculum of general education schools.

Literature analysis.

The article [3] provides information on the use of person-oriented educational technologies in mathematics classes.

[4] in the article, the historical approach to the study of academic subjects to a certain extent brings the educational process closer to scientific knowledge, and the teacher, while getting acquainted with the concepts of mathematics, asks about their history and development (mainly the services of our great ancestors) during the lesson. It is thought that the implementation of the program will increase students' interest in science and cultivate love for the Motherland.

The article [5] analyzed the issue of using didactic games in the process of teaching mathematics. It was noted that the level of organization of lessons depends on the teacher's creativity. It is said that the students will consolidate the knowledge they have received from the lesson and prepare to apply it in life.

[6] in the article, it is noted that the role of independent education in strengthening students' knowledge in today's advanced science and technology era is of particular importance. From this point of view, it is emphasized that it is very important to increase students' self-confidence, learn independently, study independently, and teach them to work independently. In addition, the aspects that should be paid attention to in the organization of independent education of students, the instructions that should be given to students were briefly discussed.

The article [7] provides a brief understanding of labor-related issues and how they are divided into types, stages of solving them, and the main laws encountered in such issues. Summarizing the considerations about what assertions we should pay attention to when solving textual arithmetical problems related to work, solutions of problems on the topic are presented as examples. It is noted that the problems solved with the given confirmations and comments will help students and independent learners of the subject to master the textual problems without difficulties.

The article [8] presents a number of theoretical and logical foundations for the development of students' creative thinking, without which it is emphasized that it is impossible to correctly solve exponential equations and inequalities. Typical variations of exponential equations and inequalities are given, as well as instructions for solving such problems.

The article [9] provides important information on what to pay attention to in order to have basic knowledge in solving inequalities using best practices in the development of education and to avoid errors in generalizing solutions. Using the algorithmic method, solutions of examples of inequalities related to fractional-rational, irrational, logarithmic and trigonometric functions are given.

[10-26] article is devoted to the analysis of the effectiveness of interactive technologies as a means of improving the quality of the educational process. Today, it is noted that the use of interactive methods in the educational process is widely introduced, which requires the humanization, democratization and liberalization of the educational process. The use of information technologies in lessons helps students develop a skill-based approach, develop their abilities, which allows them to become competent, professional individuals in educational institutions. Interactive methods are aimed at achieving high results in a short period of time without spending a lot of time and physical effort, teaching the student theoretical knowledge, acquiring skills and competencies in certain types of activities, forming moral qualities, controlling the student's knowledge and it is said that assessment requires great skill and dexterity.

The main part. The topic "Motion problems" known in school mathematics is a topic that comes after the topic "Textual problems in geometrical content" and includes problems related to the connections between speed, time and distance. Two of these quantities are given in the condition of the problem, and it is required to find the third.

Typical arithmetic problems of this type are included in the elementary school mathematics curriculum and textbooks. Although movement issues are not included as a separate chapter in the 4th grade textbook, it is advisable to start preparing for such type of issues much earlier, from the 1st-2nd grades. During this period, students can look at the following problem related to distance.

To repeat the previous topic, we use the "Find your neighbor" method (Table 1).

Table 1

№	Questions	Answers
1	What is the perimeter of a rectangle?	The perimeter of a rectangle is twice the sum of its width and height equal to
2	The formula for finding the face of a rectangle?	To find the face S of a rectangle, it is necessary to multiply its width a by its length b. $S=ab$
3	$a*a*a$ multiplication is written in the form of a^3 , how is it read?	Pronounced "a's cube" or "a cube"
4	What is the meaning of the term algorithm?	The meaning of the term algorithm is to do something means a certain sequence or rule.
5	In Europe, the name al-Khorazmi was used in the style of	Al-Khorazimi's name in Europe is Algorizmi. Used in the style of "algorithm", "algorithmus"
6	Can the remainder be greater than the divisor in division?	In division, the remainder cannot be greater than the divisor.
7	How to check that the multiplication is done correctly?	If the product is one of the multipliers then the second multiplier if, the multiplication is true, otherwise it is false. .

New topic statement: The process of solving motion problems should be started by looking at simple problems.

Problem: Two travelers from two villages set off towards each other at the same time. The first passenger walked 240 steps and the second passenger walked 360 steps before meeting the second passenger. How many steps are the distance between the two villages? By solving this problem, the students are prepared to study the problems related to the meeting motion of two bodies. Let's discuss this issue:

- What is the matter about?
- It is said that two travelers are walking towards each other from two villages.

(At this time, the teacher marks two villages on the blackboard through points A and B, connects them with a straight line cross section, and tells the students that the

image of the cross section AB can be viewed as the distance between the two villages) (picture 1)

That is:

1-picture

How did they act? - They moved towards each other - Is it known how many steps the first passenger walked until he met the second one?

- Yes, 240 steps. - What about the second passenger?

- 360 steps (The teacher shows these given lines (arrows) directed from A to B and from B to A in the cross section AB, noting that the passenger from B walked more, in the middle of the cross section as a sign of meeting, it shows the steps taken by passengers 1 and 2 until they meet (Picture 2).

2-picture

It should be said here that today teachers widely use information technologies. It is appropriate to demonstrate the condition of this problem on the computer in the form of moving people and show it to the students

- What does the problem question require us to find?

- How many steps are the distance between two villages (The teacher adds one more to the condition of the drawing on the board, that is, connects the distance AB with an arc and puts a question mark below this arc (Pic. 3).

That is

3-picture

- If the first passenger walked 240 steps and the second passenger walked 360 steps before meeting, can you find how many steps are the distance between the two villages? - Yes - By what action? - By adding 240 to 360, $240+360=600$ (steps) Answer: The distance between two villages is 600 steps.

By solving such problems, the course of action of students is "Should we meet?" "Opposite direction?" they will find out. They prepare to solve the problems of movement. Let's look at the following problem that teaches you to know another direction of action.

The process of solving motion problems should be started by looking at simple problems. Among such simple problems, include problems on finding the speed for a given distance and time of movement, problems on finding a distance based on a known speed and time of movement, and problems on finding a movement time on the basis of a known distance and movement speed. possible So, movement represents the connection between three main quantities: path (distance), time and speed. (pic. 4)

Determining the distance in terms of speed and time Teaching to solve such problems first of all begins with introducing the student to the concept of speed. This can be done roughly as follows.

- Did you, the students, ride the car? What about the train? (After receiving answers about the students riding the car and the train, it is explained that both the car and the train move, as well as other means of transport.)

For example. Let's say that the train traveled 80 kilometers (road) in 1 hour. So, the train moved at a speed of 80 kilometers per hour. Or we can say that the train was moving at a speed of 80 km/h.

In general, the path traveled by a body in a unit of time represents the speed.

Units of length are mm, cm, dm, m, km; There are units of measurement of speed, just like units of measurement of time are s (second), min (minute), hour. They can be m/min, km/h, m/s, km/min, km/s. When writing units of measurement of speed, the unit of length is first written, then a slash "/" (or "-") is placed, and time is written under the slash. For example, a train is moving at a speed of 60 km/h.

Matter. The train traveled at a speed of 80 km/h for 3 hours. How many kilometers did he travel?

Solution: $80 \text{ km/h} \cdot 3 \text{ hours} = 240 \text{ km}$. Answer: He traveled 240 kilometers. After introducing the concept of speed, the rule of finding the distance traveled according to the given speed and time is conveyed to the students.

To find the distance traveled for a given speed and time, you need to multiply the speed and time. In general, if the path traveled by a body moving v km per hour in t hours is denoted by the letter S , this path is calculated according to the formula $S=v \cdot t$.

In order to strengthen the topic, it is appropriate to look at the following issues.

Problem 1 Gulchehra travels 4 km in 1 hour. How many kilometers does he travel at such a speed in 2 hours? How about in 3 hours? What about 4 hours? How about in 30 minutes?

Problem 2 A train is traveling at a speed of 76 km/h. It is a) in 2 hours; b) How many kilometers will be covered in 5 hours?

Problem 3: "Nexia" car is moving at a speed of 90 km/h. Find the distance traveled by him in 1 minute, 10 minutes, 15 minutes, and half an hour.

Thus, the traveled distance (s) is equal to the product of the body speed (v) and the time spent (t). Tasks on finding the distance in terms of speed and time are aimed at strengthening the knowledge of students, and by performing the exercises, students learn to compare the speeds of body movement. We will consider these issues and the method of working on them.

Problem 4: The car traveled 72 km in 1 hour. How far does he go in 1 minute? In this issue, the issue of moving from a larger unit to a smaller unit is raised. Of course, while solving motion problems, students need to learn how to convert numbers into one another.

The solution to the above problem is as follows:

- 1) How many meters is 1 kilometer? $1 \text{ km}=1000 \text{ m}$
- 2) How many meters is 72 kilometers? $72 \text{ km}=72 \cdot 1 \text{ km}=72 \cdot 1000 \text{ m}=72000 \text{ m}$.
- 3) How many minutes is 1 hour? $1 \text{ hour}=60 \text{ minutes}$.
- 4) How far does the car travel in 1 minute?
 $72000:60=1200 \text{ m}=1 \text{ km } 200 \text{ m}$

Answer: The car traveled 1200 meters in 1 minute.

Problem 5: Mahira walks 50 meters when she takes 100 steps, and her father walks 90 meters when he takes 150 steps. How many steps should Mahira take to walk 180 meters? What about his father?

This problem is a complex one, involving types of motion and proportionality.

A brief statement of the problem:

Mahira 100 steps-50 m

? step - 180 m

His father is 150 steps -90 m

? step - 180 m.

The problem can be solved in different ways.

In the above question, in part 1, it is said that in how many steps will Mahira cover a distance of 180 m. In this part, we will use methods to solve the problem by bringing it to unity. 1) How many steps does Mahira have to take to walk 1 meter?

$$100:50=2 \text{ (step)}$$

2) How many steps does Mahira take to walk 180 meters?

$$2 \cdot 180=360 \text{ (step)}$$

In the second part of the problem, it is asked to determine how many steps his father takes to cover a distance of 180 meters. To solve this part of the problem, we use the method of proportional connection relations.

3) How many times are there 90 m in 180 m?

$$180:90=2 \text{ (times)}$$

4) How many steps must the father take to cover a distance of 180 m?

$$150 \cdot 2=300 \text{ (step)}$$

(His father who took 150 steps to walk 90 m, 2 times more than 90 m -2 times more than 150 steps to walk 180 m, that is, $150 \cdot 2=300$ steps need)

Answer: Mahira has to take 360 steps and her father has to take 300 steps.

We use the "Schulte table" method to concentrate the attention of the students who are bored by the lecture part of the new topic (mainly the students sitting at the back desks). For this, a picture of a table filled with numbers written in different colors is placed on the board (use these devices if there is an electronic board or TV in the room). A Schulte table contains random letters or numbers. The most

common tables are rectangular, with five rows and five columns. In the numerical interpretation, 25 numbers are placed in random order. The task of the person working with it is to find all the numbers from 1 to 25. (Figure 4) (take 2 minutes to find the numbers in a row).

Answer: Numbers from 1 to 25

(1 point for every 3 numbers) (picture 5).

9	12	18	14	16
10	21	5	15	7
23	17	24	20	1
6	4	19	11	8
25	22	3	13	2

Picture 5: Schulte chart

The 6th grade textbook was used as a basis for writing the article. Today, in the developing countries, it is used in the name of methods that form the basis of great experience in supporting modern pedagogical technologies that guarantee the effectiveness of the educational process. Using modern methods of teaching, it becomes easier for students to understand the topic and they themselves are able to explain it to other students.

In short, in the process of teaching the topic "Geometric text problems" to schoolchildren, by using the information presented in the article, it is possible to effectively organize the parts of the lesson to repeat the previous topic, explain the new topic, and strengthen the knowledge gained on the topic. can be achieved. In general, various interactive methods of education can be used to make the lesson more effective, productive and interesting [3-26].

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. B.Q.Xaydarov. Textbook for the 5th grade of general secondary schools.1-qism.Toshkent-2020.
2. To‘laganov T. P. Elementary mathematics: Arithmetic, algebra: Ped. Instruction manual for in-ts and un-ts.– T.: O‘qituvchi, 1997. -272 b
- 3.A. Sh. Rashidov Matematika darslarida ta’limning shaxsga yo‘naltirilgan texnologiyasi. Центр научных публикаций. 2021 yil. 3-son. 68-72 bet
- 4.A.Sh. Rashidov Ijtimoiy-gumanitar ta’lim yo‘nalishi talabalari uchun matematik fanlar bo‘yicha amaliy mashg‘ulotlarni o‘tkazish. Science and Education №9. С 283-291
- 5.O.O.Халлоқова. А.Рашидов Пороговое собственное значение модели Фридрикса. Молодой ученый, 2015 №15. С. 1-3
- 6.A. Sh. Rashidov Interaktivnyye metody pri izuchenii temy "Opredelenny integral i yego prilozheniya". Nauchnyye issledovaniya. № 34:3. С 21-24
- 7.A. Sh. Rashidov Yoshlar intellektual kamolotida ijodiy tafakkur va kreativlikning o‘rni. Pedagogik mahorat 2021 yil №7. 114-116 bet.
- 8.A.Sh. Rashidov. Matematika fanlaridan talaba yoshlar ijodiy tafakkurini rivojlantirish. Fan va jamiyat №3. С 45-46
- 9.A.Sh. Rashidov замонавий таълим ва инновацион технологиялар соҳасидаги илғор тажрибалар. Центр научных публикаций. 2021 yil. 3-son. 68-72 bet 8-14
10. A.Sh.Rashidov. M.F.Faxridinova. O‘quvchilarning bilimini baholashda xalqaro baholash dasturlari. “Fizika, matematika va informatsion texnologiyalarning innovatsion rivojlanishdagi o‘rni” mavzusidagi Respublika ilmiy-nazariy anjuman. Buxoro. 222-227 bet.
11. A.Sh.Rashidov. S.A.Mehmonova. Matematik analiz fanini o‘qitishda interfaol metodlar: “KEYS-STADI” metodi “Fizika, matematika va informatsion

texnologiyalarning innovatsion rivojlanishdagi o‘rni” mavzusidagi Respublika ilmiy-nazariy anjuman. Buxoro. 165-169 bet.

12. Zaripov Nozimbek Nayimovich, Hasanov Behzod Normurot o‘g‘li Options for Working with Files in the Python Programming Language International Interdisciplinary Research Journal Volume 2 Issue 3, Year 2023 ISSN: 2835-3013 c. 371-375.

13. Hasanov Behzod Normurot o‘g‘li Matritsa ustida amallar bajarish metodlari Educational research in universal sciences, 2024/3/3 c.38–45.

14. Zaripov Nozimbek Nayimovich, Hasanov Behzod Normurot o‘g‘li Python dasturlash tilini o‘qitishda funksiyalardan foydalanish metodikasi Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali 2023 Tom 1. №18 c. 15-19

15. Rustamovich, M. U. (2023). Comparative Analysis of 6th Grade Natural Science Textbooks of Uzbekistan and Turkey. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 2(3), 114-120.

16. Daminov, M. I., Kakhkhorov, S. K., & Mustafayev, U. R. (2020). STUDYING THE BASIS OF NANOTECHNOLOGY IN THE SCHOOL PROGRAM PHYSICS. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University*, 3(4), 320-324.

17. Mustafoyev O‘.R. 6-sinf "Tabiiy fan" darsligida namoyishli tajribalarning o'rni va roli//Innovations in technology and science education 2:17 (2023),p. 253-261.

18. Jabborova, G. S. (2022). Vektor fazolarda operatorlar va ularning asosiy xossalari haqida. *Science and Education*, 3(11), 17-32.

19. Jabborova G.S. Hayitova X.G‘. (2023)“Uchburchakli panjarada aniqlangan diskret Shryodinger operatorining xossalari” Tadqiqotlar jahon ilmiy – metodik jurnali, 6(14), 118-126.

20. Mustafoyev O‘. R. (2024). Maktab fizika darslarida o‘quvchilar faolligini oshirishda Sun’iy intellektning o‘rni. *Pedagogik akmeologiya*, 2(10), 218-221.

21. Jo‘rayeva N. O., Hasanova M.F. Birhad va ko‘phadni birhadga bo‘lish. *Образование и наука в ххi веке». Выпуск №26 (том 6) (май, 2022).* -632-644 стр

22. Jo‘rayeva N. O., *Образование и наука в ххi веке». Выпуск №26 (том 6) (май, 2022).* -620-631 стр

23. Jurayeva N.O. Fundamentals of Organizing Students' Independent Work Using Mobile Applications. *Child Studies in Asia-Pacific Context (CSAC)*. 2022, 12 (1); 255-266

24. Jurayeva N.O. Specific aspects and principles of the method of organizing independent education of students. *Actual problems of modern science, education and training”*. №8, Xorazm, 2022. – P. 23-27. (13.00.00; № 24).

25. Jo‘rayeva N.O. Mobile Softwareanwendungen zur Organisation unabhängiger Bildung// *Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities*. Vol. 2, Issue 1.5 (2022), – P. -661-664. (13.00.00; № 7).

26. Jo‘rayeva N.O . Mustaqil ta’limni tashkil etishda mobil ilovalaridan foydalanish. *Ta’lim va innovasion tadqiqotlar*. 2023 год №1. -273-27 b